

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Impact of formulation of photocurable precursor mixtures on the performance and dimensional stability of hierarchical cation exchange membranes

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Hansen solubility determination

Table S.1. Scores and RED of SPMA and Ebecryl 830 samples with 25 screening solvents.

Solvent	δ_D	δ_P	δ_H	SPMA		Ebe830	
				Score	RED	Score	RED
1-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone	16.4	9.3	5.9	0	2.089	1	0.381
2-methyl-2-butanol	15.3	6.1	13.3	0	1.027	0	0.598*
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	14.4	7.3	12.9	0	1.034	0	0.622*
4-vinylpyridine	18.1	7.2	6.8	0	2.169	1	0.496
Acetone	15.5	10.4	7.0	0	1.867	1	0.356
Acetonitrile	15.3	18.0	6.1	0	2.476	1	0.999
Acrylic acid	15.6	8.7	14.5	1	0.580	1	0.569
Acetic acid	14.5	8.0	13.5	1	0.879	1	0.623
Allylamine	15.5	5.7	10.6	0	1.449	1	0.471

Chloroform	17.8	3.1	5.7	0	2.567	1	0.827
Cyclohexanone	17.8	8.4	5.1	0	2.366	1	0.545
Dichloromethane	18.2	6.3	6.1	0	2.335	1	0.602
Diethylene glycol methyl ether	16.2	7.8	12.6	1	0.983	1	0.379
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	18.4	16.4	10.2	0	1.999	1	0.827
Divinylbenzene (DVB)	18.6	1.0	7.0	0	2.698	1	1.028**
Ethylenediamine	16.6	8.8	17.0	1	0.444	1	0.793
Hexane	14.9	0.0	0.0	0	3.603	0	1.456
Methanol	14.7	12.3	22.3	1	1.002**	0	1.433
Methyl methacrylate	17.5	5.5	4.3	0	2.581	1	0.719
N-methyl-2-Pyrrolidone (NMP)	18.0	12.3	7.2	0	2.068	1	0.489
Propan-2-ol	15.8	6.1	16.4	0	0.735*	0	0.825*
Styrene	18.6	1.0	4.1	0	3.079	1	1.145**
Tetrahydrofuran (THF)	16.8	5.7	8.0	0	1.911	1	0.433
Toluene	18.0	1.4	2.0	0	3.281	1	1.201**
Triethylamine	17.8	0.4	1.0	0	3.499	0	1.337

*Wrong in: the model predicts that given solvent should be outside the sphere, contrary to the experimental result. **Wrong out: the model predicts that given solvent should be inside the sphere, contrary to the experimental result.

Table S.2. List of potential solvent candidates for membrane formulations ranked according to increased distance from the middle point of the overlap of SPMA and Ebe830 solubility domains.

Solvent	Distance MP	RED SPMA	RED Ebe830	Rejection criterium
Methyl Hydrazine	1.539	0.580	0.569	price
Acrylic acid	1.541	0.580	0.569	-
Dimethyl Ethanolamine	1.637	0.664	0.484	toxicity
Ethylene Glycol Monomethyl Ether	1.783	0.571	0.606	toxicity
Isocyanic Acid	1.859	0.698	0.471	toxicity
Allyl Alcohol	1.863	0.292	0.784	UV-reactive
Propylene Chlorohydrin	1.978	0.591	0.614	price, toxicity
2,2,2-Trifluoro Ethanol	2.083	0.368	0.776	price, toxicity
Ethylenediamine	2.527	0.444	0.793	toxicity
Azidoethane	2.664	0.847	0.388	price
1-Fluoro Acrylic Acid	2.677	0.846	0.395	UV-reactive
2-Bromo Allyl Alcohol	2.708	0.597	0.716	UV-reactive
Acetone cyanohydrin	2.786	0.640	0.693	toxicity
2-Chloro Allyl Alcohol	2.792	0.585	0.739	UV-reactive
Dipropylene Glycol	2.801	0.356	0.871	-
Hexane-1,6-Diol	2.875	0.306	0.899	price

1,9-Nonanediol	2.926	0.690	0.670	price
3-Chloro Allyl Alcohol	3.025	0.615	0.754	UV-reactive
Vinyl Carbitol	3.028	0.839	0.502	UV-reactive
Ethylene Glycol Monoethyl Ether	3.033	0.809	0.549	toxicity
Ethylene Chlorohydrin	3.055	0.533	0.817	toxicity
Ethyl Carbamate	3.084	0.912	0.377	price
Methoxy Methanol	3.289	0.310	0.956	toxicity
Acrylamide	3.373	0.912	0.470	UV-reactive
1,3-Dichloro-2-Propanol	3.459	0.863	0.574	toxicity
Diethylenetriamine	3.485	0.873	0.566	toxicity
2,3-Dichloropropanol	3.530	0.876	0.574	price
3-Azidopropene	3.551	0.948	0.455	price
Diethylene Glycol Monomethyl Ether	3.557	0.983	0.379	toxicity
2,3-Butadiene-1-ol	3.687	0.669	0.830	price
2-Propyn-1-ol	3.689	0.393	0.987	price
Ethyl Lactate	3.693	0.999	0.391	-
1-Propanol	3.734	0.602	0.886	identified as bad solv.*
Acetic acid	3.740	0.879	0.623	-
2-Nitro-1-Propanol	3.838	0.773	0.768	price
Hydroxyethyl Acrylate	3.852	0.930	0.578	UV-reactive

2,2-Dimethyl-1-Propanol	3.904	0.949	0.563	price
3-Methyl Allyl Alcohol	3.926	0.819	0.740	UV-reactive
2-Propanol	3.945	0.735	0.825	identified as bad solv.*
2-Pentanol	4.089	0.987	0.554	identified as bad solv.*
Methyl Amine	4.103	0.730	0.862	toxicity
1-Butanol	4.245	0.846	0.783	identified as bad solv.*
1-Pentanol	4.267	0.983	0.614	identified as bad solv.*
2-Butanol	4.293	0.943	0.680	identified as bad solv.*
1,2-Cyclohexanediol	4.327	0.679	0.944	price
N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)-2-Pyrrolidone	4.444	0.941	0.721	identified as bad solv.*
Iso-Butanol	4.473	0.840	0.841	identified as bad solv.*
Glycidol	5.483	0.968	0.951	toxicity

*poor solubility of Ebe830 or SPMA or formation of nonhomogeneous mixture

Mechanical testing

Mechanical testing has been performed with the use of tensile testing machine (LRX, Lloyd, United States). The membrane samples were prepared for the measurement by cutting the standard specimen from each membrane sheet according to the ASTM D412 Type A specification with the mechanical press (B/36-AL, Naef, United States). The sample preload for tensile testing was set at 0.5N and the strain rate was 20 mm/min.

Table S.3. Mechanical properties of the membranes.

Membrane	Force at break [N]	Elongation at break [%]	Young modulus [MPa]
PVC-SiO ₂ substrate	22.53 ± 0.55	12.3 ± 0.31	311 ± 1
AA-hIEM	31.06 ± 1.96	5.21 ± 0.43	378 ± 39
AcA-hIEM	32.61 ± 2.63	3.46 ± 0.26	484 ± 3
DPG-hIEM	30.21 ± 0.04	4.07 ± 0.96	505 ± 7
EtL-hIEM	34.84 ± 0.65	3.47 ± 0.14	548 ± 30
Nafion 117	40.85 ± 1.02	79.86 ± 0.19	113 ± 1
CMHPES	79.10 ± 1.62	28.41 ± 0.03	285 ± 34
FKS-PET-75	55.61 ± 0.83	19.13 ± 0.96	1345 ± 65

Fabricated hierarchical ion exchange membranes show high dimensional stability due to rigid substrate, what is proved by their low elongation when compared to commercial membranes. Interestingly, thin ion exchange coatings improve the tensile strength of the hIEMs, what was observed in the increase of force needed to tear the coated membranes in comparison to the bare

substrate (PVC-SiO₂). Hierarchical IEMs reveal relatively high Young modulus due to moderately good mechanical resilience with high resistance to dimensional deformation at the same time.

Optical microscopy

The cross-sectional images of fabricated hIEMs were captured by a digital microscope (VHX-7000, Keyence, Japan) in order to evaluate the quality of obtained coatings and measure the membrane and coating thickness.

Figure S.1. Cross-sectional image of fabricated hierarchical ion exchange membranes. (1) AA-hIEM, (2) AcA-hIEM, (3) DPG-hIEM, (4) EtL-hIEM.

Cost estimation of membrane fabrication

The liquid formulation is applied on the substrate by a blade coater in a thin film with a thickness of 90 μm , fixed by the gap of a coating blade. The calculated volume of a 90 μm thick formulation coating spread on a 1 m^2 of substrate is 90 cm^3 . The estimated cost of a formulation to prepare

the 1 m² of each hierarchical ion exchange membrane was calculated as follows. For each membrane formulation, the volume needed to cover 1 m² of substrate was multiplied by the given formulation density. The calculated mass of a given formulation needed to cover 1 m² of substrate was then multiplied by the share and price of each component of a given formulation for the cost per m² estimation (table S.5). The price of each component, used for the cost calculation, is reported in table S.4.

Table S.4. Price of components of liquid formulations of membranes.

Component name	Supplier	Price [€/kg]
Acrylic acid	Merck GmbH	28
Acetic acid	POCH z.o.o.	25
Dipropylene glycol	Alfa Aesar	29
Ethyl lactate	Alfa Aesar	35
3-sulfopropyl methacrylate potassium salt	TCI Co., Ltd.	320
Ebecryl 830	Allnex SA	11
TPO	Industrial trader	20

PVP	Merck GmbH	253
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Table S.5. Cost estimation of liquid formulations of membranes.

Membrane formulation	Density [g/cm ³]	Mass per m ² [g]	Formulation cost [€/m ²]
AA-hIEM	1.22	110	10
AcA-hIEM	1.23	111	12
DPG-hIEM	1.13	102	4
EtL-hIEM	1.12	101	4

The supporting PVC-silica material is produced internally at Amer-Sil SA and is estimated to contribute from 3 to 6 €/m², resulting in the highest material cost around 18 €/m² estimated for AcA-hIEM. For a simple comparison, the use in this cost estimation a liquid formulation of perfluorinated resin e.g., 5 wt. % Nafion 1100W solution in lower aliphatic alcohols and water according to Merck GmbH, results in a material cost exceeding 330 €/m².

Further cost estimation of hierarchical membranes fabrication, employing easy scalable blade coating and UV curing processes, leads to the expected final price of the product kept below 100 €/m². The final price of the product is depending on many factors such as production yield, quality and cost management strategy. However, the target final price below 100 €/m² is much less than the market price of commercially available membranes such as Nafion 117, Ralex CMHPES and FKS-PET-75, selected as a benchmark membranes in this study. The market price of benchmark commercial membranes reaches several thousand euro per square meter.

Calculation of junction potential

According to the Ryan S. Kingsbury et al., the junction potential can be calculated from the activity-corrected form of the Henderson equation:

$$E_j = \frac{\sum_i \frac{|z_i|u_i}{z_i} [a_i(2) - a_i(1)]}{\sum_i |z_i|u_i [a_i(2) - a_i(1)]} \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\sum_i |z_i|u_i a_i(1)}{\sum_i |z_i|u_i a_i(2)}$$

,where z_i (dimensionless) is the charge number of ion i , u_i ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) is the mobility of ion i , $a_i(1)$ and $a_i(2)$ (dimensionless) is the activity of ion i in external solution and activity of ion i in electrode filling solution, respectively.

The calculation was made on an assumption of a linear activity gradients throughout the junction.

We calculate the junction potentials for normal temperature and pressure conditions and ion mobilities at infinite dilution. The calculated ΔE_j between standard calomel electrode immersed in 0.5M KCl versus standard calomel electrode immersed in 0.1M KCl is 2.384 mV. This results in a selectivity difference of around 6.5 ppt while offsetting by the junction potential. The selectivity values corrected by the junction potential offset are reported in table S.6.

Table S.6. Membrane selectivity calculated taking into account the junction potential offset.

Membrane	Selectivity
AA-hIEM	89.9%
AcA-hIEM	86.9%
Nafion 117	89.0%
CMHPES	88.0%
FKS-PET-75	85.5%

